

CLINICAL AND IMMUNOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF JUVENILE RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS

Sadikova A.M.¹, Ashurova D.T.¹, Ruzibakieva M.R.²

¹Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute

²Institute of Human Immunology and Genomics

Abstract Juvenile rheumatoid arthritis (JRA) is an autoimmune disease characterized by inflammation that targets the body's own tissues, involving complex interactions between genetic and immunological factors. This study analyzed the levels of inflammatory cytokines, including IL-8, IL-17A, and IFN- γ , in children with different forms of JRA. The research was conducted on 106 patients aged 3 to 18 years and a control group of 40 healthy children. The results showed that IL-8 and IL-17A levels were significantly higher in children with seropositive JRA, especially in the 15-18 age group, compared to the control and seronegative JRA groups. In contrast, IFN- γ levels were reduced in both forms of JRA, with the lowest levels found in seropositive cases. These findings highlight the role of cytokine imbalance in the pathogenesis of JRA and suggest that monitoring cytokine profiles may improve treatment strategies for this disease.

Keywords JRA, IL-8, IL-17A, INF γ , seronegative, seropositive

1. Introduction

The development and progression of inflammation in rheumatic diseases is caused by autoimmune mechanisms, which are based on a violation of tolerance to one's own antigens, leading to the development of an immune response against normal tissues. This process is mediated by a complex interaction of genetic, immunological factors, various infectious agents and other environmental influences, defects in hormonal and neuroendocrine regulation [1, 5, 7].

The basis of inflammation is a cascade of biochemical and immunological processes, the regulation of which is carried out by a large number of humoral mediators. Among them, cytokines occupy a special place - low-molecular proteins that ensure the process of intercellular interactions [4, 8, 12]. At present, it is the change in the cytokine profile that is considered as a possible trigger mechanism for the development of juvenile rheumatoid arthritis.

The aim of this study was to study the role of IL-8, IL-17A and INF γ in the development of juvenile rheumatoid arthritis in children and determine their prognostic significance.

2. Materials and methods

The material was collected during 2021-2023 at the Department of Cardiorheumatological Diseases of the Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute. A total of 106 patients aged 3 to 18 years were examined. All patients underwent a comprehensive clinical examination, including laboratory and in-

strumental studies. Forty healthy children were examined as a control group for comparison.

To determine the concentration of IL-8, IL-17A, INF γ in the blood serum of the study groups, a three-stage "sandwich" method was used - this is a type of three-phase ELISA "Vector-Best" (Novosibirsk, Russian Federation).

The obtained data were subjected to statistical processing using the Fisher-Student variation statistics method and the Pearson χ^2 criterion.

3. Results and discussions

When analyzing the data obtained by age of children with JRA, we obtained the following results: children aged 3 to 7 years accounted for 11.1% (n=5), aged 7 to 14 years - 57.8% (n=26), aged 14 years and older were 33.3% (n=15). When analyzing gender, a slight predominance of males (53.0%) was revealed, compared to females (47.3%). Pain in the joints of the legs and arms was detected on average in 88.6% (n=40) and 64.4% (n=29) of children, respectively. Local joint signs of JRA (limited movement, swelling) were found in 77.6% of children. Signs of intoxication (fever, general weakness, loss of appetite, tachycardia, shortness of breath) were observed on average in 39.1%. Neurological disorders (convulsions, capriciousness) were observed in an average of 37.7% of children with JRA. Analysis of somatic diseases revealed that ENT diseases were more common in children with JRA (91.1%). Cardiovascular diseases were observed in 64.4%. Anemia was detected in 53.3% of children with JRA. The incidence of nervous system diseases was 31.1%. Urinary system diseases were also detected in 20.1%, rickets in 13.2%, and dysbacteriosis in 15.6% of children with JRA.

Dysmetabolic nephropathy, ophthalmologic disorders, and allergic diseases were detected in an average of 7.74%. TORCH infection was detected in 6.67% of children with the pathology under study.

IL-8 is a chemokine with two directions of action. On the one hand, it inhibits the production of proinflammatory cytokines by macrophages, and on the other hand, it induces the production of acute-phase proteins that activate the production of corticosteroids, promote the activation of T-lymphocytes by APC, enhancing B-cell proliferation and induce the formation of immunoglobulins, stimulates hematopoiesis and the formation of platelets [6, 7, 11].

In the cohort of children aged 15 to 18 years, the highest IL-8 levels were observed in the group with the seropositive form of JRA with an average value of 38.3 ± 4.06 pg/ml, which was almost 3 times significantly higher than the values of the control group and 1.3 times higher than the values of the seronegative form of JRA (29.5 ± 3.23 pg/ml). ($P \leq 0.05$) (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. IL-8 level in children with JRA aged 15-18 years, pg/ml $P \leq 0.05$

It is known that 3 subpopulations of T-helpers (Th) play a role in immune inflammation: Th-1, Th-2, Th-0, which synthesize cytokines with different mechanisms of action. It is generally accepted that in JIA, the Th-1 subpopulation of CD4+ T-lymphocytes predominates, specializing in the production of IFN- γ , TNF- α , IL-2, IL-12. In 2003, a new type of T-helpers was discovered - Th-17, producing IL-17A. Differentiation of Th-17A occurs independently of Th-1 and Th-2 [3, 8, 11]. IL-17A exhibits pronounced proinflammatory activity, is able to induce the synthesis of various inflammatory mediators, contributing to the development of the autoimmune process. The literature contains data on the influence of IL-17A concentration in the blood serum on the development of destructive changes in joints in JIA [4, 9, 10]

When analyzing the IL-17A level, children in the group with the seropositive form of JRA had high values, which on average was equal to 41.25 ± 5.14 pg/ml and exceeded the values of the control group by 3.55 times, and when comparing it with the values of the group with the seronegative (38.3 ± 4.83 pg/ml) form of JRA, no reliable difference was found. ($P \leq 0.05$) (Fig.2)

Figure 2. IL-17A level in children with JRA aged 15-18 years, pg/ml $P \leq 0.05$

The body's own interferon system is one of the main means of protection against infections. Many pathogenic microorganisms have interferon-inducing activity [5, 8, 11].

Analysis of the interferon- γ level in children with JRA showed a deficiency in its content in both groups, but the deepest deficiency was observed in the subgroup with a seropositive form with an average value of 9.1 ± 1.13 pg/ml, which is significantly lower than the control value by 2 times and the seronegative form of JRA in children by 1.7 times. ($P \leq 0.05$) (Fig. 3)

Figure 3. INF γ level in children with JRA aged 15-18 years, pg/ml $P \leq 0.05$

4. Conclusion

Thus, the Study of a cohort of children aged 15-18 years with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis showed a significant increase in the level of IL-8 and IL-17A, especially in the seropositive form, as well as a decrease in the level of interferon- γ in both forms, with the most pronounced decrease observed in children with the seropositive form.

REFERENCES

- [1] Drozdova, E.A., Teplova S.N. The role of impaired immune response regulation processes in the pathogenesis of uveitis associated with rheumatic diseases / E.A. Drozdova,

S.N.Teplova // Bulletin of ophthalmology. - 2018. - No. 3 (124). - P. 23-26.

- [2] Starikova, A.V. Clinical and immunological criteria for predicting the course, outcomes and choice of treatment tactics for uveitis associated with joint damage in children: Abstract of a PhD thesis. – M., 2023. – 14 p.
- [3] Trunov, A. N. Cytokine imbalance in the lacrimal fluid in patients with autoimmune uveitis / A. N. Trunov, N. S. Arbenyeva, A. L. Shvayuk et al. // Bulletin of the Orenburg State University. - 2013. - No. 4 (153). - P. 270 - 273.
- [4] Edelsten, C. Epidemiology of visual loss in pediatric uveitis / C. Edelsten, M. Stanford, E. Graham // XXXIX International Congress of ophthalmology. – Sydney, 2013 – P.138.
- [5] Foster, H. The eyes have it! The need to improve awareness and access to early ophthalmological screening for juvenile idiopathic arthritis associated uveitis / H. Foster, AV Ramanan // Rheumatology (Oxford). – 2019. – Vol. 48, No. 4. – P. 330-331.
- [6] Heiligenhaus, A. Prevalence and complications of uveitis in juvenile idiopathic arthritis in a population. Based nation – wide study in Germany: suggested modification of the current guidelines / Neiwirth M., Ganser G., Heinz C. et al. // Rheumatology. – 2017 – Vol. 46. – P. 1015 – 1019.
- [7] Sanjeevi, CB Polymorphism at NRAMP1 and D2S1471 loci associated with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis / Miller EN, Dabadghao P., Rumba I. et al. // Arthritis Rheum. – 2020. – Vol. 43. – P. 1397-1404.
- [8] Diamantberger MS Du rhumatisme nouveau (polyarthrite déformante) chez les enfants. These pour le doctorat en médecine. Lecrosnier et Badae Livraires Editeurs. Paris, 2017.
- [9] Kolle G. Juvenile rheumatoide Arthritis und verwandte Kollagenkrankheiten. Klinische Aspekte Mschr Kinderheilk. 2018, 124,779.
- [10] Petty RE Classification of childhood arthritis: a work of progress. Baillieres Clin. Rheumatol., 2016, 12(2), 181-190.
- [11] Wood PHN Special meeting on: Nomenclature and classification of arthritis in children. In: The care of Rheumatic Children (Ed. E. Munthe). EULAR Publishers, Basel, 2021, 47.